

Background: The COVID-19 pandemic has had a tremendous impact on urban areas. Vaccination has been a major focus in prevention efforts, with communication focused heavily on addressing vaccine hesitancy. While hesitancy may be one factor contributing to lower vaccination rates among racial and ethnic minorities, other contributors, like access, have not been explored extensively.

PURPOSE: This cross-sectional study evaluated the number of vaccination sites in Brooklyn, NY. Researchers wanted to see if there were racial/ethnic disparities in access to vaccination sites. The analysis was conducted between February-March 2021.

WHERE: Brooklyn, New York*

**the most populated borough in NYC*

WHEN? Vaccination, testing, and vaccine site data as of February 17, 2021.

WHO? Over 2.6 million residents of Brooklyn, New York 52% identified as Hispanic/Latino/Latinx or Black

ANALYSIS SOURCES

- Population and economic information were based on the **2014-2018 American Community Survey**.
- Vaccination sites were pulled from the NYC Vaccine Finder website.
- Testing and vaccination data were pulled from the NYC Health COVID-19: Data website.

KEY FINDINGS

- **There are large areas in Brooklyn that lack vaccine sites.** These neighborhoods have higher poverty and more residents that are Black or Latinx.
- There were no vaccination sites in the district with the highest poverty rate.
- Early COVID-19 vaccination sites were primarily available in White, middle-to-upper class communities.

MEASURES & OBSERVATIONS

- The number of people within each district was divided by the total number of vaccination sites to adjust for differences in population and district size.
- Researchers found **87 COVID-19 vaccination sites** throughout Brooklyn.
- A range of **0-5 vaccination sites** were found in areas that were **less than 40% White**; whereas a range of **3-8 vaccination sites** were found in areas that were **more than 40% White**.
- The **9 districts with the highest poverty rate** had almost twice as many residents per vaccination site than the 9 districts with the lowest poverty rate.

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis suggests disparities exist in access to vaccination sites. **Areas of high poverty lack access to ample vaccination resources in comparison to other areas.** White, middle-to-upper class neighborhoods have the most access to COVID-19 vaccination sites. These patterns of access and inequities are driven by structural determinants which have long existed in Black, Latinx, and low-income communities. Concrete, multi-level solutions are needed to disrupt the disparities in COVID-19 hospitalizations and deaths.

This summary was completed in April 2022. This summary includes only results from one single study. Other studies may find different results. The study was supported by the NIH RADx[®] Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) initiative (MD013769-02S1).

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To read the published research article, visit radx-up.org.

A Research Collaboration with

The EVIDENCE (Project pErception of coVID tEsting aNd vaccine) study is a project with the grant Bridging the Evidence-to-Practice Gap: Evaluating Practice Facilitation as a Strategy to Accelerate Translation of a Systems-Level Adherence Intervention into Safety Net Practices.